

IMPACT OF HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT ON EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE: A STUDY OF TWO SELECTED CHINESE OWNED FIRMS IN LAGOS STATE

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Abstract: Human resource is the only active resource in any going concern with the ability to mobilize other resources to achieve organizational objectives. To achieve this, management often invests in the development of human capital. However, most of the past studies have not been conducted on the impact of human capital development on employee performance especially in the manufacturing industries. To fill this gap, the study examines the impact of human capital development on employee's performance in two Chinese owned manufacturing firms. Descriptive (survey) research design was used in this study and the data collected were analyzed using linear regression to highlight the relationships between its variables. Two Chinese owned manufacturing firms were considered and the population for the study was three hundred and eighty four (384) which is made up of staff of Multi-Pro Enterprise Ltd (Hypo Division) and KRS Investment Ltd. The sample size for the study was two hundred while the sample techniques used was purposive method findings revealed that Job-related experiences, Development skills acquired through academic and professional qualification and identification of training programmes have significant influence on the performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms in Nigeria. It was recommended that companies/managers should ensure that resources are allocated for trainings and any development initiatives. Finally, managers should also help employees understand the benefit of training and development based on personal development in line with organization's goals.

Keywords: Human Capital, Human capital development, Experience, Performance, Training.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human capital plays a pivotal role in every industrial organization. In managing people's talent, abilities, and capabilities, organizations strive to gradually develop some strategies for the development of its human resources thereby enhancing productivity, performance and retention. The paradigm shift from traditional people's management to development has challenged many sectors including the manufacturing sector. This shift has been a source of concern as well as strength to management of organizations whichever way it is considered. More important, however, is the fact that human capital development for contemporary organizations remains critical to their performance (Worlu & Omodero, 2016; Surbhi, 2015). This is the reason why many organizations, including the Chinese-owned firms, invest in their human capital to improve performance metrics (Shafiq & Hamza, 2017; Adebisi, 2014).

Human capital development plays a vital role in improving and nurturing competencies. In order to maintain competitive edge in a knowledge driven sector, management teams must continuously evolve different strategic thrusts. One of those strategies rests on improving the caliber and qualities of employees. This explains the importance of human capital development. This scenario makes the study of what determines human capital development imperative and with the identification of this, organizations such as Chinese-owned firms would know the direction to take to continuously enhance their employees' development. Although there are mixed reactions from the existing literature on what could serve as determinants of human capital development, what remains clear is the understanding that those determinants could be classified along internal and external contexts (Ekundayo & Odhigu, 2016; Oleka, Sabina & Onyeze, 2014; Adeleye, Adegbite & Aderemi, 2014).

Human capital development are necessary for improving quality in the organization and to facilitate this, programmes such as seminars, trainings, mentoring, conferences are established. Therefore, through these programs employees are encouraged to focus their attention by means of critical thinking skills (Adeniji & Osibanjo 2012; Amoah-Mensah, 2016). According to Agbiogwu, Ihendinihu and Azubike (2016), human capital development basically aimed at empowering employees to perform their job at a level in which the organization's performance standards, quality and other activity requirements of that organization are met. Hence, human capital development can be seen as intangible asset in an organization.

Most often manufacturing firms are floated to achieve profit, this motive can be threatened with undeveloped human capital. This implied that these firms to some extent can only be profitable when their employees are seasoned, knowledgeable, skilled and professional in their activities (Worlu & Omodero, 2016; Ogbo, Ezeobi & Ituma, 2013). Therefore, in the manufacturing context, human capital development can be summed up as the total personnel cost which covers: expenditure on training both off and on the job; salaries and wages; expenses on re-training and attending conferences/workshops for the purpose of staff development. Studies have been conducted on human capital development in both developed and developing countries (Noe, 2012; Sanyal & Hisam, 2016; Adeyemi, 2011; Aluko & Aluko, 2011), however, internal or specific impact of human capital developments on the performance of employees in the manufacturing perspective remains blurred especially the Chinese firms. In Nigeria different organizations such as Standard of Nigeria (2015) and World Bank (2017) have called for the assessment of the determinants of human capital development in the manufacturing sector at different times.

1.1 Statement of the Research Problem

Organizations need to stay in the competitive environment and to achieve this, employees with competency and right attitude who are ready to perform at their best are needed. Human capital development (HCD) has become a global issue in human resource deployment. There is a need to develop employees' knowledge, skills and abilities to enrich their job related experience. Hence, human capital development has become an activity that helps to develop a competent workforce in order to achieve individual and organization goals (Asfaw, Argaw & Bayissa, 2015; Adeyemi, 2011; Aluko & Aluko, 2011; Vinesh, 2014). However, debates among scholars have ascertained that human capital development is very important to the improvement of both employees and organization performance. The business environment is becoming more dynamic and the human resources department need to close the gap between changing requirement of a job and the skills and knowledge required to perform the task because at this stage, certain job functions became redundant.

The expectation from human capital development by corporate firms has become very high in Nigeria and the negligence of the expectations by those companies has resulted to a very turbulent environment for them (Siddiqui, 2017; Vinesh, 2014). However, it has been observed that educational gap among staff and inadequate academic / professional backgrounds are prevalent in the manufacturing firms in Nigeria (Okafor, 2013; Siddiqui, 2017). Service/product quality is often affected by the results of the unskilled or inadequate staff in the workplace.

Literatures reviewed indicated that several studies were conducted on human capital development and employees performance but have not critically identifies impact of human capital development on employees performance. Also few of such studies conducted in the manufacturing sector none of such studies was carried out in Chinese owned firms thereby creating a gap.

Thus, this study investigated the extent to which human capital development has contributed to employee performance in two Chinese-owned manufacturing firms in Lagos state.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this research is to examine the impact of human capital development on the performance of employees of Chinese-Owned firms, in Lagos State.

The specific objectives are to:

1. To examine the influence of job-related experiences on the performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms
2. To investigate effect of developments skills acquired through academic and professional association on the performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms
3. To examine the role of training programmes on the performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms

1.3 Research Questions

This research seeks to answer the following questions.

1. To what extent can job-related experiences influence the performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms.
2. To what extent does developmental skills acquired through academic and professional association has effect on employees performance in Chinese owned firms
3. In what ways can training programmes impact on the performance of employees in the Chinese owned firms

1.4 Research Hypotheses

Based on the research objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated for this study

1. **H₀**: Job-related experiences have no significant influence on performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms.
2. **H₀**: Development skills acquired through academic and professional association has no significant effect on employees' performance in the Chinese-Owned firms.
3. **H₀**: Implementation of training programmes have no significant influence on the performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Human Capital

Human capital can be described as total innate abilities which is endowed in people. It is the stock of potentials, skills, competence, knowledge, creativity, attitude, and personal abilities deposited in people who are channeled towards achieving economic value. Human capital is also an approach to staffing which regard employees as an asset whose present value can be measure and also their future value can be improved through investment in training and development

2.2 Human Capital Development (HCD)

Human capital development is regarded as an organization activity which aims at improving job performance within the organization. It is a continuous process that focuses on helping employees to broaden their knowledge and skills which help them achieve greater performance. Through this process, information and knowledge is transferred in which employee put into practice to achieve effectiveness. Training takes place after an employee has been recruited and selected. It prepares employees for a new work system. It is also done for existing workers (Sanyal and Hisam, 2015;).

According to Vinesh (2014), human capital development is the field which is concerned with organizational activity aimed at bettering the performance of Individuals and groups in organizational setting. The importance of human capital development cannot be overemphasized as the success of an organization lies on the human factor who work within the organization. They are able to make meaningful contribution towards the achievement of organizational goals. Before human capital development takes place, it is important to identify training needs (Siddiqui, 2017; Asfaw, et al., 2015) in which an evaluation is carried out after the training process. Organizations also need to carry out compulsory training and re-training for staff in all forms.

According to Shafiqand and Hamza (2017), organization should try and increase their human capital development with the technological changes and present educational system in order to develop proper training programmes. Adeniji and Osibanjo (2012) defined training as “the planned efforts by a company to facilitate employee’s learning of job-related competencies”. They include knowledge, skills and behavior (Asfaw, et. al., 2015; Amoah-Mensah, 2016; Ogbo, Ezeobi & Ituma, 2013) and the application to their day to day activities. Training of personnel is always considered necessary when the need for training has been identified, this is the difference between the actual performance of an employee and the expected performance. it helps the organization design training programs fit to provide the knowledge that employees need.

There is continuous pressure for efficiency and if the organization does not respond to this pressure, it may find itself rapidly losing its market. Human capital development impacts skills and knowledge to employees in order that they contribute to the organization’s efficiency and be able to cope up with the pressures of changing business environment. The viability of an organization depends to a considerable extent on the skills of different employees, especially that of managerial cadre, to relate the organization with its environment (Amoah-Mensah, 2016; Agbiogwu, Ihendinihu & Azubike, 2016; Ogbo, Ezeobi and Ituma, 2013). Therefore, in any organization, there is no question of whether to train its employees or not, the only choice is that of following a particular human capital development method. Some of the objectives include:

- i. To increase employee’s knowledge: employees need specific knowledge in doing specific jobs. Training tend to assist employees to have a sense of job satisfaction and job security thereby increasing the morale and level of productivity of such employee which in return contribute to the success of the organization and reducing absenteeism and turnover (Agbiogwu, et al, 2016; Abbas, 2014). This helps the employee attain some level of confidence while working. For example, a customer service personnel should have full knowledge of the products and services offered by the organization. This is to avoid service failure.
- ii. To improve overall performance of the organization: training prepares employees to make meaningful contributions to the organization (Amoah-Mensah, 2016; Armstrong, 2010; Ogbo, Ezeobi & Ituma, 2013). This creates a positive impact thereby improving organization performance. An employee who is properly trained will be familiar or accustomed with his or her job and hence will need little or no supervision to perform his or her job adequately or effectively. Based on this reason time and effort wastage is minimized
- iii. Prepares employees for higher jobs by developing advanced skills: training helps employees acquire knowledge and skills required for development. some job roles require special, adequate skills and knowledge to be able to attain them (Ogbo, Ezeobi & Ituma, 2013; Sanyal & Hisam, 2016). The possibilities of employees making mistakes are bound to happen if the employee does not have the required skill and knowledge to perform a particular task. However, the need for employees to get trained reduces the rate at which accidents occur and hence employees to become more capable in performing their jobs.
- iv. To cope with technological advancement: there has been an improvement in product and service quality as a result of technological advancement. Therefore, organizations must employees to make changes as technology changes. Human capital development helps in enhancing the productivity (Agbiogwu, et al, 2016; Amoah-Mensah, 2016) and efficiency level of employees. Properly trained employees portray both quality and quantity performance and hence there is effective and efficient use of resources such as material, money, man and time.
- v. To prevent skill obsolescence: HCD helps employees acquire skills such as communication skills, listening skills, problem solving skills etc. this will help increase employee morale. According to Stewart (1996), the purpose of human capital development can have significant effects on the management or an organization in an optimistic and most importance way. The need to assist managers develop their capabilities to face changing circumstances successfully, however implementing training programmes (Amoah-Mensah, 2016) and development activities (Ogbo, Ezeobi & Ituma, 2013) can ensure that the required abilities needed to manage the uncertainties connected with the change are acquired.

Human capital development has become a must requirement for employees to acquire skills and perform at their best. Therefore, when employees exhibit some signs that will affect the organization productivity, it is required to carry out human capital development programmes. Some of the signs include:

- i. Low productivity: There is need for training when a productive employee starts to show signs of decreasing productivity and performance as a result of some factors. Therefore, it is important to engage the employee and try to identify issues surrounding the low performance and then take action to bridge the gap in the performance of the employee. Amoah-Mensah (2016) also indicated that training employees on the job can be seen as a method of enhancing the abilities and skills of employee which hence, lead employee's commitment. Therefore, the abilities of an organization to know the best ways to improve commitment level of every employee in the organization are very vital.
- ii. High accident and absenteeism rate: Workplace accidents happens unintentionally and it can be reduced greatly in the organization. All employee needs to be trained on their job on how to use equipment and also provide specific safety requirements at work. High absenteeism rates from employees can affect the organization negatively in terms of productivity (Amoah-Mensah, 2016; Armstrong, 2010; Ogbo, Ezeobi & Ituma, 2013) and morale. It is important to take actions to reduce absenteeism by keeping them motivated and ensuring a safe and healthy work environment.
- iii. High rate of rejections in the quality of output: Human capital development is required when the quality and performance of a product or service is not acceptable. This can be through bringing in new and better ways to achieve quality and also ensuring that employees have the ability to perform at their best. Employees are mostly referred to as the blood stream of every business or organization. Hence it will be said that the success or failure of any organizations depends on the performance of the employees in the organization. However, performance can be described as the total endeavors that contain the abilities and capacities that an employee put in their jobs or duties. It was observed by Kinicki & Kreitner (2007) that employees who are happy and derive large satisfaction from their jobs are more likely to increase the rate at which they perform and hence organizations find it easier to motivate these employees that perform well to achieve certain targets for the organizations. Moreover, training practice has helped in providing employees with skills and also boosting their capabilities to improve their performances (Armstrong, 2010) and also training has increased the level of individual and organization competencies (Sanyal & Hisam, 2016).
- iv. Negative attitude at work: when employees are not motivated, they start to exhibit negative attitude at work which can lead to low morale. This can be due to knowledge inadequacy that results in frustration and poor performance. There is need to organize a training program to motivate employees and boost morale.

2.3 Employee Performance

The inability of organizations to retain or sustain performance through the talented employees within the workforce can be regarded as a major problem in most organization. However, employees are regarded as the pillar and a vital resource in every organization and research has showed that those organizations that are successful in the future are those who are able to retain the highly skilled employees in their organization. It was also reported by Bridges (2007), that the distraction and confusion of employees will lead to decrease in the retention rate and hence leading to a change in the organization's operation.

Performance will therefore be viewed as a commitment to constantly engage in business operation within an organization on a continual basis (Zineldin, 2000; Sanyal & Hisam, 2016). Employee performance can be seen as the ability of organizations to keep workforce that is effective and also meet the operational objectives of the organization through the implementation of strategies (Mita, 2014; Armstrong, 2010; Sanyal & Hisam, 2016).

However, there are some factors that have been considered to be determinants of employees performance and these factors have been viewed by various scholars. Ghapanchi & Aurum (2011) enumerated factors such as training opportunities, organization culture, remuneration and benefits, fair and equal treatment. Christen (2014) acclaimed that employee performance can be enhanced through the provision of conducive environment, good management relationship, implementation of social and development programs, freedom and a sense of responsibility, good compensation scheme, flexible working conditions and a balanced working operation as regards work and life.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

2.4.1 Decision Making Theory

The decision-making theory has been reviewed by diverse scholars, examples includes Weber (1947); Mintzberg (1973); however, Iyayi (2002) and Miller, Hickson & Wilson (2003) worked on the theory. The theory has been assumed by many scholars that the decisions made in organizations are usually rational and hence encourages organizational

efficiency leading to better performance within the organization (Miller et al, 2003). It has been said that objectives are set to achieve the reason why organizations were established. In line with this statement, Dessler (2015) opined that the abilities of decision making to take advantage of opportunities and also engage in problem solving skills can be regarded as the essential idea of decision making. This means that the success or failure of every organization is determined by how well the organization is able to establish decisions that will guide its operations. Its assumption can be said to be more relevant to the extent at which organizations want to succeed and also improve its performance. It is very important to emphasize that decision making in the manufacturing sector is necessary to facilitate the achievement of their main objective which is profit maximization. It is therefore right to accept that placing the success and failure of every organization is valid. It can be proven that management might implements strategies for recruitment process to attract competent employees into the organization; however, it can be said that the ability of management to make rational decisions so that these employees are trained can help retain this competent talents.

According to Siddiqui (2017) and Worlu & Omodero (2016), the decision made to direct the thing that are done within the organization and also lead to the formulation of the future decisions that will guide its operations are viewed to be very substantial and hence, seen to be of a great importance to the stakeholders of the organization. Banjoko (2006) in process of highlighting the distinctive responsibility job satisfaction plays in encouraging employees stay in an organization which leads to improved performance stated that, “if the belief that a happy worker is a productive worker hold true, then the view that satisfaction causes performance may hold ground.” Ikezua (1999) opined that organization achievement of objectives which might include the enhancement and the provision of goods and services can only be made possible through the individuals that have been created for it. It means that are more likely to be motivated, stay or be committed to an organization if there are appropriate retention strategies put in place. Sanyal & Hisam (2016) opined that the employees are viewed to be the most important, significant and productive resource of every organization and it is because these employees are the ones who work together to ensure that the goals and objectives of an organization are achieved. Hence, for organization to keep ensuring that their goals and objectives are achieved the best strategies to train and retain these competent employees should be put in place and such strategies should include the implementation of training and development programs.

2.5 Empirical Review

Umer and Ahmad (2013) conducted a research on the “impact of training on employee retention”. In his study he used a sample size of 100 employees in both the public and private sector which he evaluated using the convenience sampling technique. However, the data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and regression analysis. The findings of the study indicated that a positive relationship did exist between employee retention and training practices. Hence, employee’s decision to remain or leave an organization is greatly dependent on the ability of the organization to conduct training programs.

A study was also examined by Nkosi, (2013) on the “effects of human capital investment on employee commitment, retention and performance”. In carrying out this investigation, the local municipality in South Africa was used as the case study. A sample size of 130 respondents were used to collect data using the convenience sampling technique, however in collecting these data a structured questionnaire which was computed using the likert scale method was distributed. The analysis and interpretation of the data collected was done using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) method. In the quest to check the reliability and the validity of the data, the study employed the use of Cronbach alpha and Keiser – Meyer- Okin analysis respectively. The result was based on the fact that there is great effect of human capital investment on retention, employee commitment and performance. The result also further confirmed that human capital investment practices is largely connected with the commitment of employees within the organization and on the basis of employee retention; the result stated that there is a positive connection between training and the decisions made by employees to remain in the organization.

Terera & Ngirande (2014) examined the ‘impact of human capital development on employee satisfaction’. This study was conducted on administrative staff member using the universities as the case study. The study adopted the qualitative style of research methodology where by a sample sizes of 120 respondents were evaluated to get diverse response and analysed using regression analysis. The findings showed that human capital development cannot be regarded as the only factor that allows employees remain in an organization, other factors includes; global exposure, experiences and financial rewards. The result also indicated that a positive relationship exists between job satisfaction and retention. It further stated that the degree at which employees stay within an organization is dependent on the level of satisfaction that is got from that organization.

Udu& Ewans (2016) conducted a study on human capital development on employees performance; a study of double diamond plastic manufacturing firm The study used correlation design and sample of 166 was drawn from the population. Structured questionnaire was used to collect information from the respondents. The data collected was analyzed using parsons product moments correlation. The study revealed that there is a positive correlation between on the job training and quality of employees job performance with correlation coefficient of (r) of (0.97). Also that there is positive correlation between off the job training and workers efficiency with correlation coefficient of (r) of (0.84). The implication of this is that human capital development enhance employees job performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study was quantitative and question-based survey was adopted in eliciting information and the items in the questionnaire were adapted with modifications from the works of De- Silva, Opatha, & Gamage (2016); Ball and Junemann (2012). The descriptive (survey) research design was used and the population of the study comprises 384 middle and lower level management staff of two chinese-owned firms, Multi-Pro Enterprise Ltd (Hypo Division) and KRS Investment Ltd. Sample size for the study was 200 and was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table. Sampling techniques adopted was purposive The data collected were analyzed using multiple linear regression via statistical package for social science to highlight the degree of variance and prediction of the variables.

Data Presentation

The frequency count, simple percentage, and regression were used in analyzing the data collected from the use of questionnaires. A total number of two hundred (200) copies of questionnaire were administered to the employees of two selected Chinese-owned firms in Lagos state, Nigeria. However, one hundred and seventy-four questionnaire were returned out of which twenty six (26) wrongly filled. The valid questionnaire was one hundred and forty eight (148) indicates the valid rate of 74%, which is substantial enough to make a conclusion.

Research Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis as shown below:

1. H_0 : Job-related experiences have no significant influence on performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms in Lagos State.

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F
1	.495 ^a	.245	.236	.35373	44.872
Co-efficient Analysis					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.833	.305	.495	4.633	.000
Job-related experiences	.517	.066		6.639	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Job-related experiences					
b. Dependent Variable: Employee performance					

The results from the model summary table above revealed that the extent to which the variance in the dependent variable (employees' performance) is explained by the independent variable (job-related experiences). In this case the R square is .245 if expressed by a percentage will be 24.5%. This connotes that 24.5% variance of employees' performance can be explained by job-related experiences. The adjusted R square shows that .236 that is 23.6% variability of the independent variable (by job-related experiences) while the standard error of the estimate indicates .35373 which signifies error term. The ANOVA table shows that the F value is 44.872 at .000^a Significance level. The prediction level is .517 which connotes that a unit increase in job-related experiences employees will eventually lead to increase in employees' performance by 51.7%. The significance level below 0.05 implies a statistical confidence of 95%. Thus, the null

hypothesis (H_{01}) was rejected; while the alternative hypothesis (H_{a1}) which says that by job-related experiences have significant effects on employee performance is accepted.

Hypothesis Two

2. **H₀**: Development skills acquired through academic and professional associations has no significant impact on employees' performance in the Chinese-Owned firms in Lagos State.

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F
1	.289 ^a	.083	.0674	.31423	26.833
Co-efficient Analysis					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.598	.274	.289	3.875	.000
Academic and Professional Qual.	.201	.071		2.744	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Academic and professional qualification					
b. Dependent Variable: employee performance					

The results from the model summary table above revealed that the extent to which the variance in the dependent variable (employees' performance) is explained by the independent variable (Academic and professional qualification). In this case the R square is .083 if expressed by a percentage will be 8.3%. This connotes that 8.3% variance of employees' performance can be explained by academic and professional qualification. The adjusted R square shows that .067 that is 6.7% variability of the independent variable (academic and professional qualification) while the standard error of the estimate indicates .31423 which signifies error term. The ANOVA table shows that the F value is 26.833at .000^a Significance level. The prediction level is .201 which signifies that a unit increase in academic and professional qualification of employees will ultimately lead to increase in employees' performance by 20.1%. The significance level below 0.05 implies a statistical confidence of 95%. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) was rejected; while the alternative hypothesis (H_{a1}) which says that both the academic and professional qualification have significant effects on employee performance is accepted.

Hypothesis Three

3. **H₀**: Implementation of training programmes have no significant influence the performance of employees in the Chinese-Owned firms in Lagos State.

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F
1	.226 ^a	.051	0.043	.32755	24.571
Co-efficient Analysis					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.427	.472	.226	4.623	.000
Training programmes	.188	.075		3.755	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Training programmes					
b. Dependent Variable: employee performance					

The results from the model summary table above revealed that the extent to which the variance in the dependent variable (employees' performance) is explained by the independent variable (training programmes). In this case the R square is .051 if expressed by a percentage will be 5.1%. This connotes that 5.1% variance of employees' performance can be explained by training programmes. The adjusted R square shows that .043 that is 4.3% variability of the independent variable (training programmes) while the standard error of the estimate indicates .32755 which signifies error term. The ANOVA table shows that the F value is 24.571 at .000^a Significance level. The prediction level is .188 which signifies that a unit increase in the implementation of the training programmes will result to increase in employees' performance by 18.8%. The significance level below 0.05 implies a statistical confidence of 95%. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) was rejected; while the alternative hypothesis (H_{a1}) which says that the implementation of the training programmes have significant effects on employee performance is accepted

4. CONCLUSION

Human capital development is important as it should be seen not only as a human resource function, but also as an instrument of change that can strengthen the relationship between employees and the management. It has also provided employees with the opportunity to expand their knowledge while benefiting the organization alongside. It has helped organizations close the gap that may arise as a result of technological advancement. Training programmes has been of lot benefits to both the organization and employee as it provides returns on investment made on human capital worth it. The implication is that human capital development is strongly linked with labour in other words, the quality and education of staff in the selected firms have a positive relationship with human capital development.

In recent and past literatures there has been traces of proof that human capital training and development affects directly or even indirectly the performance of employees in the organization. When employees are trained and developed they are able to get, acquire and improve their skills that help them perform well at work and involve themselves in decision making processes in various levels of the organization. In studies prior to this, human capital development components (especially training and development and career development) are used as antecedents, drivers or factors of employee performance. This indicates that as quantity, quality and education increases, employee performance also increases. This finding has supported the fact that employees are important factor determining organizational performance and success as suggested by Ogbo, Ezeobi and Ituma (2013) and Shafiq and Hamza (2017).

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends as follows:

- i. Management of organizations should give training support ensuring that employees are able to put into practice acquired knowledge. The organization must provide a conducive learning environment and also encourage employees to acquire new knowledge and skills.
- ii. When human capital development programmes are organized, there is need for evaluation. This shows the outcome of training. Assessing training needs helps to bridge the gap between a current performance and desired performance. Wrong and irrelevant identification of these needs becomes an obstacle in training and development. In order to achieve effective human capital development, employees must show interest by participating and applying new knowledge to their jobs. Therefore, the human resource department of an organization should engage employees on the benefits of human capital development and also conduct a survey to know employee's area of interest

6. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Managers play a vital role in human capital development because of the need to motivate employees. Human capital development cannot be entirely left to the human resource department; managers also need to participate in these activities. Managers have a closer relationship with team members; therefore, they can find out where employees are lacking and the knowledge and skills needed to improve productivity. Managers should ensure that resources are allocated for trainings and any development initiatives. Managers should also help employees understand the benefit of human capital on personal development in line with organization's goals.

Further research can be carried to determine the effect of human capital development on overall employee engagement. Researchers should delve into other techniques of human capital development in other to create a broader perspective on

how the practice can be fully optimized and the best output can emerge from the practice. Further research can be carried out in a comparative manner to other sectors of the economy not just the oil and gas industry. Also, government parastatals can also be considered for this practice in Nigeria.

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